

Law Governing Copyright

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Abstract

Creativity is one of the most important factor in the progress of a society and no civilized society can take the risk of ignoring its importance. Creativity being one of key factors in the economic and social development of a society needs certain protection. Laws governing Copyright in India provides that required protection to the efforts of writers, artists, designers, dramatists, musicians, architects and producers of sound recordings, cinematograph films and computer software. The protection provided by the Copyright law creates an atmosphere conducive to creativity which encourages them to create more and also motivates others to create.

Keywords: Copyright, intellectual property, Term of Copyright.

INTRODUCTION

Copyright, like Patent, trademarks and industrial designs is a form of intellectual property. According to World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), intellectual property refers to creation of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce. Intellectual property rights are the legal rights (IPRs) given to creators of intellectual property. IPRs usually give the creator of intellectual property the right to exclude others from exploiting the creation for a defined period of time. Intellectual property laws provide the incentives that foster innovation and creativity and strive to ensure that the competitive struggle is fought within certain bounds of fairness.

In India the first Copyright Act was passed in the year 1914. The Act, presently in force was legislated in the year 1957 and is known as Copyright Act, 1957 which was amended by Copyright (Amendment) Act, 1999.

Copyright is a kind of intellectual property the importance of which has increased enormously in recent times due to the rapid technological development in the field of printing, music, communication, entertainment and computer industries.

Meaning and Definition of Copyright

According to Oxford Dictionary, the word 'Copyright' is derived from the expression 'copier of words'. The word 'copy' is presumed to date back to circa 1485 AD and was used to connote a manuscript or other matter prepared for printing. According to Black's Law Dictionary word Copy means transcript, imitation, reproduction of an original writing, painting, instrument or the like.....".

According to Oxford English Dictionary Copyright is an exclusive right given by law for a certain term of years to an author, composer etc, or his assignee, to print, publish and sell copies of his original work.

According to Black's Law Dictionary "Copyright is the right in literary property as recognized and sanctioned by positive law. An intangible incorporeal right granted to the author or originator of certain literary or artistic production whereby he is invested for a specified period with the sole and exclusive privilege of multiplying copies of the same and publishing and selling them."

Section 14 of the Copyright Act, 1957 defines copyright as the exclusive right to do or authorize others to do certain acts in relation to –

1. Literary, dramatic or musical work;
2. Artistic work;
3. Cinematograph film; and
4. Sound recording.

Characteristics of Copyright

Section 16 of the Copyright Act provides that no Copyright exists in any work except as provided in the Copyright Act. Thus Copyright is a creation of specific statute i.e. Copyright Act, 1957. Unlike trademarks, there is no such thing as common law copyright. A copyright is a form of intellectual property because the product over which the right is granted is the result of utilization and investment of intellect.

Copyright is also a 'monopoly right' restraining the others from exercising that right which has been conferred on the owner of the copyright. Since it is prohibitory in nature, it is also called a 'negative right' i.e. a right to prevent others from copying or reproducing the work.

The moral basis for protection under copyright law rests on the principle that "the law does not permit one to appropriate to himself, what has been produced by the labour, skill and capital of another." That's why there is no copyright in ideas. Copyright subsists only in the material form in which the ideas are expressed.

Works in which Copyright subsists –

Section 13 of the Copyright Act provides the lists of the works in which copyright subsists. It says that subject to the provisions of this section and the other provisions of this Act, Copyright shall subsist throughout India in the following classes of works, namely –

- (a) Original literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works
- (b) Cinematograph films, and
- (c) Sound recording.

Literary work includes computer programmes, tables, compilations including computer databases. Dramatic work includes any piece for recitation, choreographic work or entertainment in a dumb show, the scenic arrangement or acting form of which is fixed in writing or otherwise but does not include a cinematograph film.

Musical work means, work consisting of music and includes any graphical notation of such work, but does not include any works or any action intended to be sung, spoken or performed with the music. For instance, an actor's movements while rendering the song in a movie cannot be copyrighted.

An artistic work means a painting, a sculpture, a drawing (including a diagram, map, chart or plan), an engraving or a photograph, whether or not any such work possesses artistic quality, a work of 'architecture' meaning any building or structure having an artistic character or design or any model for such building or structure.

Cinematograph film means any work of usual recording on any medium produced through a process from which a moving image may be produced by any means and includes a sound recording accompanying such visual recording and cinematograph shall be construed as including any work produced by any process analogous to cinematography including video films.

Sound recording means a recording of sounds from which such sounds may be re-produced regardless of the medium on which such recording is made or method by which the sounds are produced.

In case of literary, dramatic or musical work, the owner has the exclusive right to reproduce work in any material form including the storing of it in any medium by electronic means, to issue copies to the public, to perform or communicate the work to the public, to make cinematograph film or sound recording in respect of the work, to translate or make any adaptation of the work.

In case of computer programmes, the owner has exclusive right to sell or give on hire, or offer for sale or hire any copy of the programme. A new right under this category has been added by the Copyright (Amendment) Act, 1999 i.e. to sell or give on commercial rental or offer for sale or for commercial rental any copy of the programme. In India a computer programme is protected as a literary work.

In case of cinematograph film, a producer has exclusive right to make copy of the film including photograph of any image forming part thereof, to sell or give on hire, or offer for sale or hire any copy of the film and to communicate the film to the public.

Author and Ownership of Copyright

Since there is no copyright in an idea, hence the originator of an idea is not the owner of the copyright. The person who gives concrete form to the idea becomes the owner of the copyright.

According to Section 17 of the Copyright Act, the author of the work is the first owner of the Copyright in the work. Section 2(d) of the Act defines 'author' in relation to various categories of works. It says 'author' means—

- (i) in relation to a literary or dramatic work, the author of the work,
- (ii) in relation to a musical work, the composer
- (iii) in relation to an artistic work other than a photograph, the artist
- (iv) in relation to a photograph, the person taking the photograph
- (v) in relation to a cinematograph film or sound recording, the producer and
- (vi) in relation to any literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work which is computer generated, the person who causes the work to be created.

The author of a newspaper report is the person who writes it and not the person supplying the news. A journalist who writes a news story on the life story of another on the basis of such a narration made to him is the author of the story so published.

Section 17 of the Copyright Act provides that the author of the work will be the first owner of the copyright but the Act also provides situations where an author is not the first owner of copyright. When a photograph is taken, portrait or painting is drawn in return of a valuable consideration, then the person giving the consideration is the owner. When literary, dramatic, or artistic work is created by the author during the course of employment under a contract for service then in that case the employer is the owner. But any work done beyond the terms of the course of employment will be considered as the personal work of the author and he will be considered as the first owner of copyright in that work. Like teacher is the owner of the book written by him during this employment since he is employed to teach and not to write books.

Ownership of copyright in examination question papers vests in the paper setter where no contract to the contrary exists. The paper setter in such a case is the author and owner and not the Board of Examination / University / College or the authority for whom the question papers are set.

The plan of a building or a structure is the copyright of the architect. His ownership of copyright can be eliminated only by an agreement to the contrary. The client is not authorized to make copies of the plan except for his study. He cannot use the pre-existing plan even for making an extension of the building constructed on the basis of the previous plan. An author of the work becomes owner thereof, the moment work is created.

Assignment / Licence of Copyright

Section 18, 19 and 19A of the Copyright Act provides the provisions for the assignment of the copyright. It may be for the whole of the rights or for part of the rights only. Assignment of copyrights may be general, i.e. without any limitation being placed on the assignee or the assignment may be subject to certain limitations. Assignment may be for the full term of the copyright or for a limited period of time. It may be on a territorial basis i.e. for a particular territory or country.

An assignment of copyright is valid only when it is in writing signed by the assignor or by his duly authorized agent. The assignment instrument shall identify the work and specify the rights assigned and the duration and territorial extent of such assignment. When the period of assignment is not stated, the period shall be deemed to be five years from the date of assignment.

Copyright can be assigned even in respect of future works of the author before their coming into existence. But in that case, the assignment will take effect only when the work comes into existence.

Copyright is a kind of personal movable property. It can be transferred by assignment, testamentary disposition or by operation of law. When the owner of copyright whether it is published or unpublished, dies, the copyright in that work will pass on to his personal representative as part of the estate by operation of law. The Act also provides for the relinquishment of copyright. Section 21 of the Act says that the author of a work may relinquish all or any of the rights comprised in the copyright in the work by giving notice to the Registrar of Copyright.

An interest in a copyright can also be transferred through licence. But the rights granted in case of licence are limited. In such a case the ownership in the rights remains with the author, whereas in the case of assignment, the ownership in the rights is transferred to the assignee. The owner of the copyright in any existing work or in respect of future works may grant any interest in the right by licence but it should be in writing and signed by him or by his duly authorized agent.

Infringement of Copyright and its remedies

Copyright Act confers certain exclusive rights on the Copyright owner which entitles him to reap monetary benefits. If any of those rights are exercised by a person other than the owner of the Copyright without his permission i.e. either through assignment or license, it constitute infringement of the Copyright. Since Copyright is granted for a specific period of time, hence whether an act is an infringement or not would depend on the fact whether copyright is subsisting in the work or not. In case the copyright in the work has expired, the work falls in 'the public domain' and any act of reproduction of the work by any person other than the author would not amount to infringement.

There are three kinds of remedies against infringement of Copyright, namely : civil remedies, criminal remedies and administrative remedies.

Injunction, damages or account of profit, delivery of infringing copies and damages for conversion are the available civil remedies.

Imprisonment of the accused or imposition of fine or both, seizure of the infringing copies are the criminal remedies.

Administrative remedies consist of moving the Registrar of Copyrights to ban the import of infringing copies into India when the infringement is by way of such importation and the delivery of the confiscated infringing copies to the owner of the copyright and seeking the delivery.

Conclusion

The purpose of recognizing and protecting the Copyright of an author is to statutorily protect his work and inspire him to exercise his creative faculties further. A copyright confers exclusive right on the copyright owner 'inter alia', to the reproduction of the work in a material form, storing the work in any medium by electronic means, publication of the work, performance of the work in public, making of its adaptations and translations. These rights are conferred on the owner of the copyright to enable him to reap monetary benefits.

Reference

1. Das, Jatindra Kumar (2021), Law of Copyright PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
2. Scaria, Arul George, Piracy in the Indian Film Industry, Copyright and Cultural Consonance, Cambridge University Press
3. Intellectual Property Rights, A Manual E.D. and IPR Unit, BITS Pilani
4. International Copyright Order, Copyright office, Government of India.
5. Rathod, Sandeep Kanak, Fair Use : Comparing Us and Indian Copyright Law
6. Gopala Krishnan, N.S.; Agitha, T.G. Principles of Intellectual Property, Eastern Book Company
7. Copyright Act, 1957
8. Wadhera, B.L., Law Relating to Patents, Trade Marks, Copyright, Designs and Geographical Indications, Universal Law Publishing Company Pvt. Ltd.
9. Naryanan, P., Intellectual Property Law, Eastern Law House.

